

STUDIES IN THE NAPHTHALENE SERIES. PART II. SOME REACTIONS OF THE $-\text{CH}_2\cdot\text{CO}-$ GROUP.

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β -3:4-Dimethoxybenzoylpropionic acid failed to yield 1:4 diketone. 1-Keto-6:7-dimethoxy-1:2:3:4-tetrahydronaphthalene condenses smoothly with aldehydes. Derivatives with aromatic aldehydes are crystalline in most cases but the ketone does not give any *isonitroso* derivative; its benzylidene derivative on oxidation gives *m*-hemipinic acid.

The present investigation has as its object a new synthesis of *m*-hemipinic acid and a study in the reactions of the $-\text{CH}_2\cdot\text{CO}-$ group. The problem arose in the attempted synthesis of 3:4-dimethoxy- β -ethyl-octahydrophenanthrene by one of us (R.H.S.). In this connexion 1-keto-5-bromo-7:8-dimethoxy-1:2:3:4-tetrahydronaphthalene has been prepared by cyclising γ -2-bromo-4:5-dimethoxyphenylbutyric acid. This bromo-ketone on oxidation should give a derivative of hemipinic acid but 1-keto-6:7-dimethoxy-1:2:3:4-tetrahydronaphthalene, obtained by the ring-closure of γ -3:4-dimethoxyphenylbutyric acid should give *m*-hemipinic acid. Thus the syntheses of two important acids could be effected from one source. In the synthesis of *m*-hemipinic acid it was contemplated that 1:4-diketone-6:7-dimethoxy-1:2:3:4-tetrahydronaphthalene and 1-keto-6:7-dimethoxy-1:2:3:4-tetrahydronaphthalene would give benzylidene derivatives on condensation with benzaldehyde, which on oxidation would give the desired acid or it could be synthesised by acid hydrolysis of the *isonitroso* derivatives. Attempts to yield 1:4-diketone by cyclising- β -3:4-dimethoxybenzoylpropionic acid or its ethyl ester in the presence of phosphorus pentoxide, zinc chloride, acetic anhydride, sulphuric acid, etc., have been unsuccessful.

1-Keto-6:7-dimethoxy-1:2:3:4-tetrahydronaphthalene does not give *isonitroso* derivative on treatment with amyl nitrite in presence of acid or alkaline catalysts (*Ber.*, 1901, **34**, 1487; 1882, **15**, 1326; 1887, **20**, 2194; 1893, **26**, 241; 1896, **29**, 2605) but it condenses smoothly with aldehydes. The derivatives of acetaldehyde, formaldehyde and crotonaldehyde are all oily liquids and the compounds with aromatic aldehydes are in most cases crystalline products. The following derivatives, 2-benzylidene-, 2-(*o*-, *m*-, *p*-methoxy)-benzylidene-, 2-(3:4-dimethoxy)-benzylidene-, 2-cinnamylidene-, 2-(*o*-, *m*- and *p*-nitro)-benzylidene-2-furfuryl-1-keto-6:7-dimethoxy-tetrahydronaphthalene, have been prepared and 2-benzylidene derivative has been oxidised with potassium permanganate in neutral solution. The reaction yields an acid, m.p. $174-78^\circ$ (m.p. of *m*-hemipinic acid 172° ,

J. Chem. Soc., 1897, 664; m.p. 195°, *ibid.*, 1901, 400; m.p. 1910°; *ibid.*, 1902, 1046, m.p. 175°, *ibid.*, 1910, 1136) in extremely poor yield. The conditions of oxidation in order to improve the yield of the acid are yet to be fixed up; as we have to stop this work for the present we are publishing the results so far achieved.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Condensation of 1-Keto-6:7-dimethoxy-1:2:3:4-tetrahydronaphthalene with Aromatic Aldehydes: 1-Keto-2-benzylidene-6:7-dimethoxy-1:2:3:4-tetrahydronaphthalene.—To a boiling solution of benzaldehyde (6 g.; 1 mol.) in absolute alcohol (125 c.c.) ketone (8.5 g.) was added in portions. On adding potassium hydroxide (2 g. in 10 c.c. of water) the solution turned yellow and it was kept simmering on a sand-bath for 2 hours. The solution on cooling yielded benzylidene derivative, m.p. 129°, which on recrystallisation from chloroform-alcohol mixture (1:1) was obtained in light yellow silky needles, m.p. 131°. It is soluble in alcohol, acetone, ethyl acetate and readily soluble in chloroform and soluble in petroleum ether. (Found in material dried at 100° in *vacuo*: C, 77.12; H, 6.11. $C_{20}H_{18}O_2$ requires C, 77.55; H, 6.12 per cent).

1-Keto-2-(o-methoxy)-benzylidene-6:7-dimethoxy-1:2:3:4-tetrahydronaphthalene.—*o*-Methoxybenzaldehyde (1.1 g.), alcohol (30 c.c.), ketone (1.5 g.) potassium hydroxide (0.5 g. in 2 c.c. of water) were treated as in the previous case and the solution after refluxing and cooling deposited yellow needles, m.p. 143°. On recrystallisation from alcohol-chloroform cream-coloured shining needles (m.p. 152°) soluble in ethanol, acetone, ethyl acetate and chloroform were obtained. (Found in material dried at 100° in *vacuo*: C, 73.95; H, 6.17. $C_{20}H_{20}O_4$ requires C, 74.07; H, 6.14 per cent).

1-Keto-2-(m-methoxy)-benzylidene-6:7-dimethoxy-1:2:3:4-tetrahydronaphthalene.—The solution of *m*-methoxybenzaldehyde, ketone and potassium hydroxide in alcohol was refluxed for 2 hours and on dilution with water *m*-methoxybenzylidene derivative separated as a crystalline mass, m.p. 131°. It was obtained as cream-coloured hexagonal needles, soluble in acetone, chloroform, ethyl acetate and ether on recrystallisation from alcohol-chloroform mixture. (Found in material dried at 100° in *vacuo*: C, 73.49; H, 6.3. $C_{20}H_{20}O_4$ requires C, 74.07; H, 6.14 per cent).

1-Keto-2-(p-methoxy)-benzylidene-6:7-dimethoxy-1:2:3:4-tetrahydronaphthalene.—The above experiment was repeated with *p*-methoxybenzaldehyde and the *p*-methoxybenzylidene derivative was obtained in yellow needles,

m.p. 153°. On repeated crystallisation from alcohol-chloroform it had m.p. 159° and was soluble in the usual organic solvents. (Found in material dried at 100° in *vacuo*: C, 73.7; H, 6.27. $C_{20}H_{20}O_4$ requires C, 74.07; H, 6.14 per cent).

1-Keto-2-(3:4-dimethoxy)-benzylidene-6:7-dimethoxy-1:2:3:4-tetrahydronaphthalene.—Methylvanillin (1.6 g.), alcohol (20 c.c.), ketone (1.8 g.), potassium hydroxide (0.25 g. in 2 c.c. of water) after refluxing gave needles (2 g.), m.p. 148°. It was obtained as cream-coloured needles, which crystallised from alcohol-chloroform, m.p. 148°. It is soluble in methanol, ethanol, acetone and ethyl acetate. (Found in material dried at 100° in *vacuo*: C, 70.91; H, 6.14. $C_{21}H_{22}O_5$ requires C, 71.18; H, 6.24 per cent).

1-Keto-2-furfuryl-6:7-dimethoxy-1:2:3:4-tetrahydronaphthalene was obtained from furfuryl aldehyde (0.79 g.), alcohol (20 c.c.), ketone (1.2 g.) potassium hydroxide (0.2 g. in 2 c.c. of water). The red solution after refluxing for 2 hours gave a yellow solid (1.5 g.), soluble in acetone, ethyl acetate, ether and chloroform, m.p. 151°.

1-Keto-2-(3:4-methylenedioxy)-benzylidene-6:7-dimethoxy-1:2:3:4-tetrahydronaphthalene was obtained by condensing piperonal (1.2 g.) with the ketone (1.5 g.) as light yellow needles (1.4 g.), m.p. 180°, soluble in ethanol, chloroform and acetone. On recrystallisation it had m.p. 182°. (Found in material dried at 100° in *vacuo*: C, 70.63; H, 5.43. $C_{20}H_{18}O_4$ requires C, 71.00; H, 5.32 per cent).

1-Keto-2-cinnamylidene-6:7-dimethoxy-1:2:3:4-tetrahydronaphthalene was obtained in yellow needles, m.p. 155°, soluble in the usual organic solvents. On recrystallisation it had m.p. 160°. (Found in material dried at 100° in *vacuo*: C, 77.30; H, 6.26. $C_{21}H_{20}O_5$ requires C, 78.75; H, 6.25 per cent. $C_{21}H_{20}O_5, \frac{1}{2} H_2O$ requires C, 77.69; H, 6.31 per cent).

1-Keto-2-(m-nitro)-benzylidene-6:7-dimethoxy-1:2:3:4-tetrahydronaphthalene was obtained from *m*-nitrobenzaldehyde (1.2 g.), ketone (1.5 g.), potassium hydroxide (0.5 g. in 2 c.c. of water) and alcohol (30 c.c.). The solution on adding potassium hydroxide turned dark in colour and at once solidified. The condensate was filtered at the pump and washed with a little alcohol, m.p. 175°. On recrystallisation from alcohol-chloroform it was obtained in light yellow shining plates, m.p. 190°, soluble in ethanol, methanol, acetone, and insoluble in ether and petroleum ether. (Found in material dried at 100° in *vacuo*: C, 67.21; H, 5.23; N, 4.36. $C_{19}H_{17}O_5N$ requires C, 67.25; H, 5.01; N, 4.12 per cent). Likewise derivatives with *o*- and *p*-nitrobenzaldehydes were prepared but they are dark brown amorphous powder and melted at 152° and 270° respectively and are soluble in chloroform, acetone and ethyl acetate. (Found in *p*-nitrobenzylidene derivative after

drying at 100° in *vacuo* : N, 4.13. $C_{19}H_{17}O_5N$ requires N, 4.12 per cent).

Condensation of the Ketone with Acetaldehyde, Formaldehyde and Crotonaldehyde.—Acetaldehyde (0.56 g.), alcohol (20 c.c.) and ketone (1.5 g.) were refluxed in the presence of potassium hydroxide (0.5 g.) and on working up a thick oily substance was obtained. Likewise similar products were obtained with formaldehyde and crotonaldehyde.

Oxidation of 1-Keto-2-benzylidene-6:7-dimethoxy-1:2:3:4-tetrahydro-naphthalene with Potassium Permanganate.—To a solution of the ketone (4.26 g.) in acetone at 0° finely powdered potassium permanganate (6 g.) was gradually added with constant stirring. The pink solution was filtered at the pump from the slimy precipitate and after destroying excess of potassium permanganate with alcohol it gave some unreacted ketone. The slimy precipitate was dissolved in water and its ether extract after acidification with dilute hydrochloric acid gave a mixture of benzoic acid and an acid with a brownish tinge, m.p. $174-78^{\circ}$. The latter was not sufficient for further characterisation and confirmation. During the course of work some sticky products were also obtained from which nothing definite could be isolated.

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